

EFFECT OF STATIC MAGNETIC FIELD ON GAMMA RADIATED CARBON-POLYSULFONE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

X-ray diffraction, dilatometry, mechanical and magnetic measurements of the structure and properties of carbon plastics with polysulfone matrix subjected to gamma radiation with an intensity of 10^9 rad have revealed a certain rivalry between creative and destructive processes. A complicated character of changes in the tensile strength, glass temperature and magnetic susceptibility as a function of the radiation dose and the magnetic field intensity has been found to be associated with the formation of intermolecular bonds and free radicals, internal tensions and their relaxation, as well as orientation of the parts of molecular net in the magnetic field.

INTRODUCTION

The development of space, nuclear, and electronics industries required the creation of new polymer materials able to retain high service qualities under external energetic effects, in particular, under conditions of the effect of various types of ionizing radiation (IR). It is known [1,2] that under the effect of IR, cross-linking and breakdown processes occur in polymers, and the presence of double bonds and aromatic rings in macromolecules promotes an increase in resistance of polymers to IR. At the same time strong magnetic field can affect the processes of cross-linking in polymers by orientation of the structural elements caused by the great value of anisotropy of their magnetic susceptibility [3].

This article presents the results of studying the change in the structure and properties of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) with a thermoplastic matrix – aromatic polysulfone – as a function of the absorbed dose of gamma radiation in the presence of static magnetic field. In view of the presence in polysulfone macromolecules and in carbon fibers of a large number of aromatic rings and double bonds providing high radiation resistance of the composite, irradiation was carried out up to large values of absorbed doses (10^9). At the same time aromatic rings and double bonds have the greatest values of magnetic susceptibility [3].

EXPERIMENTAL

We investigated specimens of orthogonally reinforced composite KTMU-1 with a thickness of 1.3 mm made from aromatic polysulfone PSF-150 (in the form of film) and carbon ribbon (ELUR-0.08P) that absorbed various gamma-radiation doses. The change in the structure and properties as a consequence of IR was studied with the use of methods of x-ray diffraction analysis, dilatometry, and mechanical transverse bending tests.

The composites were irradiated on the radiation circuit of an IRT-5000 nuclear reactor in the loop of the radiation source in the form of a cylinder with an inside diameter of 90 mm and height of 300 mm. As the radioactivity carrier we used the isotope ^{113}In of the liquid metal alloy In-Ga-Sn close to eutectic in composition. Under steady operating conditions the total radioactivity of the circuit is about $1.4 \cdot 10^6$ Ci with an average gamma radiation energy of 1.148 MeV and dose rate in the cylindrical radiation source of 2000 rad/sec.

Diffraction of x-rays on the CFRP specimens was studied on a DRON-3M diffractometer with the use of the transmission photography method in the interval of angles $2\Theta = 8-60^\circ$. The diffraction patterns were recorded in the equatorial direction (relative to the upper layer of the carbon ribbon) and the angle of 45° to the direction of reinforcement. For an exact determination of the angular positions of the peaks of the diffuse maxima, scanning the angular ranges of the amorphous halos with a step of 0.1° and with a pulse rise time at each step of 60 sec was carried out. The error of determining the angular positions of the peaks of the diffuse maxima in such a photography scheme did not exceed 0.05° .

The dilatometric curves of carbon fiber-reinforced plastic KTMU-1 in the direction perpendicular to the reinforcement plane were recorded on the UIT-70M device for investigating thermomechanical properties and dilatometric measurements of polymers. Linear feeding of the specimen was carried out at a rate of $2,5^\circ\text{K}/\text{min}$ up to 520°K . Cooling occurred according to the exponential law. The dilatometric feeding and cooling curves are recorded on x-y recorder.

For conducting the transverse bending test, we used CFRP specimens in the form of a strip with a rectangular section cut in the direction of the principal axes of orthotropy. The tests were conducted on an MTS universal test machine. The specimen was loaded at a rate of 10 mm/min. The distance between supports was 42 mm. The digital values of the load, deflection, modulus of elasticity, and ultimate strength were put out to a digital printer. Six specimens were tested for each value of the absorbed dose.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Faraday's capacitor method. An electronic microbalance was used to measure the force acting on the specimen after it was placed in the gap of an electromagnet and subjected to a nonuniform magnetic field. The field was turned on and off repeatedly in the experiment. Figure 1 presents a block diagram of the unit used to conduct the experiments. The electronic microbalance (EM) had a sensitivity of $1\ \mu\text{g}$. The electromagnet (ET), with pole pieces, established a magnetic field with a constant gradient inside a volume $1\ \text{cm}^3$. The magnetic field was stabilized by a current source (FSS) with a relative instability of 0,05% at a current of 30 A. When necessary, specimen temperature was controlled through the setting mechanism (SM) of an RU5-01M unit and a VRT-2 temperature regulator (TR). The vacuum system made it possible to obtain a vacuum of 10^{-2} Pa or to perform measurements in a test medium. The measurement part of the system was comprised of three channels and included a digital voltmeter (DV) and electronic signal switch (SS). Each channel could be used to make independent measurements of temperature, the compensation signal from the microbalance, and the voltage of the magnetic field. The timer (TMR) of the unit generated command pulses to activate the DV and SS and ensure the transmission of data to the punch (P) and digital printer (DPR).

Figure 1. Block diagram of the unit used to measure magnetic susceptibility. The notation is explained in the text.

Experimental data obtained at room temperature on the magnetic susceptibility of KTMU-1 specimens was analyzed on a computer with the use of an application package written in FORTRAN. The total error of measurement of magnetic susceptibility was no greater than 1,5%. The sensitivity threshold $\chi \sim 5 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$. The data we obtained were compared with the results of x-ray diffraction analysis, dilatometry, and mechanical tests of the given specimens in transverse bending.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows diffraction patterns of polysulfone film and CFRP specimens: equatorial and taken at angle of 45° to the reinforcement direction. On diffraction pattern 3 there are two diffuse maxima: the first corresponds to scattering on the polysulfone matrix and the second characterizes the distribution of distances between the scattering centers along the axis of the carbon fiber macromolecules. The equatorial diffraction pattern is characterized by three diffuse maxima. The first and third amorphous halos have the same nature as the first and second maxima of diffraction pattern 3. The second halo corresponds to distribution of distances between carbon-fiber macromolecules. The shift of the peak of the first diffuse maxima on the equatorial diffraction pattern toward large angles compared to the analogous maximum of diffraction pattern 3 is due to the effect of the nearby maximum having a large intensity and corresponding to the intermolecular distances in the carbon fibers. The intensity of this maximum considerably decreases with photographing at an angle of 45° to the reinforcement direction, and it does not affect the angular position of the peak of the amorphous halo corresponding to x-ray scattering on the polysulfone matrix. Some shift of the amorphous halo characterizing intramolecular scattering in carbon fibers on diffraction pattern 3 toward large angles compared with the equatorial diffraction pattern is due to the presence of fragments of carbon fibers whose orientation does not coincide with the axis of the carbon filaments. The macromolecules in such fragments were not subjected to additional stretching during formation of the fibers and, consequently, a smaller average distance between scattering centers along the macromolecule is characteristic for them. Small shifts of the peaks of the amorphous halos of CFRP having a nonmonotonic character as a function of the absorbed dose indicate a high radiation resistance of components of the composite. The shifts are due to cross-linking and breakdown processes in the material under the effect of IR and occurrence of internal stresses related to them.

Figure 3 shows dilatograms of heating and cooling of the KTMU-1 specimens treated by various gamma-radiation doses which were taken in the direction perpendicular to the reinforcement

Figure 2. Diffraction patterns of polysulfone film (1) and initial CFRP specimens: equatorial (2) and taken at angle of 45° to the reinforcement direction (3).

plane. Several temperature intervals of constant values of the thermal expansion coefficient (TECs) are observed on the dilatograms of heating above the glass-transition temperature T_g of the matrix. This is related to relaxation of internal stresses occurring during formation of the composite owing to the difference of the TECs of the matrix and filler, as well as a result of the effect of gamma radiation on the material. On the cooling curves (see Fig. 3b) for all specimens there are only two regions of constant values of the TEC. The high temperature region corresponds to a high-elasticity state of the matrix and the low-temperature region to the glassy state. Relaxation of internal stresses during cooling to T_g is not observed, which can be explained by the high rate of cooling and large relaxation times characteristic of aromatic polysulfone as a consequence of considerable rigidity of its macromolecules. From the cooling curves we determined T_g of the polysulfone matrix of the gamma-irradiated CFRP: for an absorbed dose of 0 and 10^3 rad, $T_g (\pm 2^\circ\text{C}) = 153^\circ\text{C}$; for 10^4 rad, 152°C ; for 10^5 rad, 151°C ; for 10^6 rad, 157°C ; for 10^7 rad, 163°C ; for 10^8 rad, 160°C ; for 10^9 rad, 139°C . It is seen that the value of T_g begins to increase as a result of irradiation with a dose of 10^6 to 10^8 rad. For a dose of 10^9 rad it decreases markedly and becomes less than for the initial composite as a consequence of the dominance of breakdown processes over cross-linking (Fig. 4a)

The results of transverse bending tests of the KTMU-1 specimens subjected to the effect of various gamma-radiation doses are given in Fig. 4b. The dependence of the change in elastic and strength characteristics on the absorbed dose has a nonmonotonic character. At the initial stage of irradiation (10^5 and 10^4 rad) the number of intermolecular cross-links is probably small and they can be regarded as microdefects creating local zones of stress concentration, which can serve as the centers of generation of cracks during loading. With an increase of the absorbed dose to 10^5 rad, the number of cross-links increases, and the three-dimensional network being formed with a possible increase of adhesion of the matrix to the composite due to the formation of bonds between macromolecules of polysulfone and carbon fiber increases the elastic and strength properties of the composite. The decrease of strength and modulus of elasticity at a dose of 10^6 rad is related to the occurrence in the material of considerable internal stresses, which decrease with further irradiation (10^7 rad) as a consequence of an increase of breakdown processes. The most stressed bonds begin to break first of all, which leads to a decrease of the level of internal stresses and to a corresponding increase of mechanical characteristics. For doses of $10^8 - 10^9$ rad

Figure 3. Dilatograms of heating (a) and cooling (b) of CFRP specimens treated with various gamma-radiation doses taken in the direction perpendicular to the reinforcement plane: 1) initial; 2) 10^3 rad; 3) 10^4 rad; 4) 10^5 rad; 5) 10^6 rad; 6) 10^7 rad; 7) 10^8 rad; 8) 10^9 rad.

breakdown processes in the composite begin to dominate to a considerable extent over cross-linking processes, due to which the tensile strength and modulus of elasticity decrease.

Figure 4c shows the dependence of the change in the magnetic susceptibility of specimens which had absorbed different doses of gamma radiation on the strength of the magnetic field. The susceptibility χ of the initial specimens remained constant for all values of field strength H . The absolute value of susceptibility for the specimens which absorbed a dose of 10^3 rad was greater than the analogous value for the initial specimens. The increase in the diamagnetic properties of the composite in this case can be attributed to the formation of additional cross-links between the macromolecules of the polysulfone matrix. The magnetic susceptibility of these specimens is also independent of the strength of the magnetic field. Along with an increase in the number of cross-

Figure 4. Dependence of tensile strength σ , modulus E (a), glass temperature T_g (b), magnetic susceptibility χ (c) on radiation dose D and magnetic field strength H .

links in the composite, an increase in the absorbed dose leads to the accumulation of unreacted radicals with paramagnetic properties. This in turn leads to a decrease in $|\chi|$, which is now nearly independent of H (dose 10^4 rad).

With further exposure (10^5 rad) we see an increase in $|\chi|$ as field strength increases. The initial value of $|\chi|$ ($H = 2500$ Oe) is lower than in the previous case, due to an increase in the concentration of unreacted radicals. The increase in susceptibility seen with an increase in field strength is connected with the orientation of elements of the structure having diamagnetic properties. It is evident that when the number of cross-links increases along with the absorbed dose, it is relatively large fragments of the network rather than individual atoms that are oriented by the field (the atomic orientations are easily disturbed by thermal motion). Moreover, these

fragments are less subject to the misorienting effect of thermal collisions with neighbors.

The relation $\chi(H)$ becomes extreme in character when the absorbed dose is increased to 10^6 rad. For low values of magnetic field strength, $|\chi|$ had the highest value among all the investigated specimens in that case. Such a result is connected with the fact that the highest tensile stresses are created under the given circumstances. This was established in dilatometric studies of the irradiated specimens (Fig.3). The range of temperatures in which the internal stresses relax is highest for such specimens, and even negative values of the coefficient of thermal expansion are seen within this range. When H was increased up to 4500 Oe, there was a nonmonotonic decrease in $|\chi|$. This decrease was probably connected with relaxation of internal stresses in the material under the influence of magnetic field. A further increase in the strength of the field H was accompanied by orientation of the diamagnetic moments of fragments of the network and an increase in $|\chi|$.

At a dose of 10^7 , degradation caused by relaxation of internal stresses begins to be manifest (see Fig. 3), which in turn leads to a reduction in $|\chi|$ compared to previous case (Fig 4c).

Degradation becomes considerably more advanced with a further increase in absorbed dose (10^8 rad). There is a decrease in $|\chi|$ (which increases with increase of H) due to an increase in number of free radicals. The temperature interval associated with internal stress relaxation comes to be roughly the same as in the initial specimen (see Fig. 3).

Degradation processes proceed even further in a material that absorbed a dose of 10^9 rad. There is a significant narrowing of the interval connected with internal stress relaxation (curve 8 in Fig.3), a decrease in the glass point to a level below the value of initial specimen (Fig. 4a), and deterioration in mechanical characteristics (Fig. 4b). The specimens which absorbed a gamma radiation dose of 10^9 rad had the lowest $|\chi|$ (at H = 2500 Oe), which is connected with the accumulation of a large number of free radicals in the material. The rate of increase in $|\chi|$ for these specimens when field strength was increased from 2500 to 6000 Oe was nearly the same as in the specimens which absorbed 10^7 – 10^8 rad. The values of $|\chi|$ increased at an increasing rate with a further increase in H. It is evident that when degradation has proceed sufficiently far, the fragments of the matrix network (which have diamagnetic properties) are less connected to one another by continuous macromolecules and may therefore be more readily oriented by a magnetic field.

CONCLUSION

The study results show that the change in the magnetic susceptibility of specimens which have absorbed different doses of gamma radiation depends on the strength of magnetic field and correlates with the change in their mechanical properties, thermal behavior, and structural changes.

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